

Øystein Fjeldbo and Diana Lindbjerg

GJØRME

Performance Paper

Video of presentation can be found [here](#)

Gjørme 0.1

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Abstract

“all our individual efforts to stand out are futile, we all just decay into the same smiling pile of shit!” User_5884499
(insert: emoji of smiling pile of shit)

This paper is a description for the initial stages of the collaborative project Gjørme. GJØRME is a web crawler / multimedia installation / performative piece aiming to render its creators obsolete in its creative process. The project is an exploration of boundaries between automated and manual labour using Instagram as a datasource for colour profiling, analysis and interpretations in RGB, CMYK and audio outputs. The aim of the project is to make an installation with a freestanding automated apparatus that, if prompted by a user, can analyse and output without human intervention.

The title ‘Gjørme’ is a norwegian word for ‘mud’ or ‘muddy’ and was chosen as a worktitle as it describes what happens with subtractive colours (CMYK), when you physically mix them and end up with a dark brownish colour as opposed to additive colours (RGB) in light that mix into white. Distinguishing between these two systems is a key component in both the method and the motivation for the project.

Keywords: automation, colour profiling, social media, digital, analogue, performance, CMYK, RGB

Introduction

Summer 2019: The User - Diana Lindbjerg, approached the Future Daughter - Øystein Fjeldbo, and wanted to discuss matters of colour and online presence.

Dear Future Daughter

- Have you ever mixed beautiful colours in paint and ended up with an unsatisfying brownish colour on the paper? I was looking at Instagram the other day, thinking about how most profiles have a very strict colour profile. If you look at a random profile and squint your eyes, you realize that it is quite easy to pick out three to five colours that dominate the images. Maybe that in all our attempts of creating profiles on social media designed to 'stand out' and promote our individuality and creative efforts we all just end up producing different samples of similarly unsatisfying brownish output. On our last project together in 2016 we worked on social media feedback loops and I was thinking that we could work together again with these thoughts in mind. We could explore what happens if we extract colour profiles from Instagram profiles, creating different outputs and see where we can take it. My theory is that all our individual efforts to stand out are futile, and I predict that we all just decay into a colour scheme and noise. Basically resembling the same smiling pile of shit!

Dear User_5884499

- I have blended sounds until I've reached a thick dense mass of sound, where nothing stands out except the sensation of some sort of massive multitude. I guess that would be analogous to the myriad of voices enabled by the democratization of the internet. Your theory is intriguing. There is absolutely a perceived homogeneity in these efforts you talk about. Do you think your theory would also apply the other way around - to taste? That there is some kind of aesthetic ideal that under the right circumstances all humans can enjoy? We could automate this as an experiment. Set up a kitch-machine to plunder material en masse and use this sampled material to create new material. Its creations can be broadcasted back online, testing its appeal to the people.

What is GJØRME?

The title 'Gjørme' is a norwegian word for 'mud' or 'muddy' and was chosen as a worktitle as it describes what happens with subtractive colours (CMYK), when you physically mix them and end up with a dark brownish colour as opposed to additive colours (RGB) in light that mix into white. Differentiating between these two systems is a key component in both the method and the motivation for the project.

GJØRME is a web crawler and could be described as a multimedia installation and performative piece. The goal is to render its creators obsolete in the creative process. An autonomous web crawler is collecting material, using this sampled material to create new audiovisual content both digitally and translated into physical space. Its creations will be broadcasted back online. In this version of the piece, the bot will be working on the social network Instagram. Instagram is an ideal platform for automated collecting and publishing. The idea is to insert the bot in a network of users, where the bot might inspire its peers and at the same the bot is fed by its peers. In a long-form feedback loop the bot will go through the content of its list of followers (the audience may follow the bot and thus feed it with input). The bot will here extract content from these profiles, determining a mean color profile of each one. Firstly the color profile will form the basis of an automated digital processing, projected in the room. Secondly the analysis will be translated to colour pigments through a motorized squirting of paint into a glass container. By allowing the colour profiles to mix, each of these processes will present a changing colour over time. The digital, additive system will most

likely create a light tone almost white light and the physical subtractive colours will most likely mix to a brownish colour. Similar to the visual part, any audio from videos the bot might encounter will be sampled. The bot will use an automated cut-up technique to create a continuous audio collage from the sampled material, which in turn will be time stretched and averaged in frequency and amplitude, thus building an ambient composition in realtime based on the profile's sonic content. The output of the bot will be recorded both in image and audio, and snippets will be uploaded to its Instagram profile, hopefully making contact with others out there. This automated process is inspired by the ideas and creative output from plunderphonics (Oswald 1985)

Example of process development: The development of the project is a constant dialogue between the digital extractions and analogue samples. By testing the crawler and then translating this digital outputs into additive and subtractive colour systems.

Figure 1. Extraction test and analogue subtractive colour test.

Technical aspects

The web crawler is written in Python, and utilizes a combination of keyboard emulation through `pyautogui` library (Sweigart 2019) and computer vision through the `OpenCV Python` library (Heinisuo, 2020). Thus the process is transparent, as one can observe Python interacting with the browser, stopping for each new element it discovers while it analyses and records the content. When encountering a video, the video will play through and the audio is patched into `Csound` for sampling and processing. Python does the color extraction through averaging the RGB values for each pixel in a frame. For the ICL presentation this information was then sent to `Max` and `Jitter` for a simple visual overview design. In the future, this information will also be converted into `CMYK` and output as physical paint through digitally controlled fluid pumps, setting the mix of Cyan, Magenta, Yellow and Key for each analyzed image, before it is squirted into the muddy overall mixture. At the core of the auditory content presented at ICL was averaging the amplitude and frequency spectrum of the sampled audio material through `pvsMOOTH` (Lazzarini 2006), and partial tracking through the `partials` opcode (Lazzarini 2005), creating an automated ambient composer.

Aesthetic philosophy

Figure 2. Spectrum of sunlight. Homemade spectrometer. Diana Lindbjerg (2020)

Figure 3. Gjørme extract of profile of User_5884499. Diana Lindbjerg/Øystein Fjeldbo. (2020)

We use the spectrometer as an analogy to understand what 'Gjørme' does. Not splitting the white light into rainbows but extracting reference points in photographic images normally perceived as figurative signs and signifiers. The project is informed by ongoing research into the ontology of the photographic image and colour theory. Our source material for 'Gjørme' - Instagram - consists of digital images that we popularly recognize as photographs, however the way they are organized in a fixed size, format scroll or grid formation highly informs our reading of them and both maker and viewer. "The apparatus does as the photographer desires, but the photographer can only desire what the apparatus can do." (Flusser, Roth and Poster, 2011) By breaking down the information we are presented with in a fixed interface or 'apparatus' and presenting this information through a 'new lens' we can maybe understand different aspects of what we output in social media as well as creating a completely new output.

Ambition

At the moment we are really just at the starting point of the project, using very crude techniques for extracting a relatively low amount of data. For the final part of GJØRME, and as the goal of the project as a whole, it would be optimal to utilize a machine learning component for analyzing encountered content in a lot higher detail than what is achieved by us today. Implementing an understanding or at least an estimate perception of what is present in a picture, a video or an audio stream would open up a new world of possibilities where the bot can build up an archive of what sort of information is posted to the web and also connecting this information to what content has gotten the most interaction in the form of likes. Thus the computer is building statistics on what kind of content is most heavily consumed and enjoyed by the end user, and it's possible to imagine the bot to be able to react to end user interaction (likes), and tweak its output to try to please the end user base. The next step would then be to experiment with different ways of building content containing new iterations of this information. It is easy to imagine image and audio synthesis to be the first base here, but also robotized drawing or playing should be tested for its possible X factor of purely existing in the «raw» outside world before it is documented and again uploaded to the web. The complexity of the analysis and creation is of course infinite, and thus the project may grow for the entire foreseeable future. The same idea of finding an average still applies to this infinite complexity level, where the bot is averaging content. GJØRME is of course an experiment. It is meant as an examination of human taste as it applies to web content. And if it really is so that our preferences are homogenous, then we might just as well automate the creation.

Figure 4. flowchart sketch of a potential interface. We have used The image of a Zoltar fortune telling machine as an idea of how you could interact with a potential new interface. By scanning an Instagram profile and then receiving different types of output. For example a spectrum (additive colours), a physical sample of 'gjorme' (subtractive colours) and an abstracted audio output. D.Lindbjerg/Ø.Fjeldbo (2020)

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